

Good Corporate Governance, Corporate Social Responsibility on Firm Value and Financial Performance as Moderating Variables

(Case Study on Companies Listed on the IDX)

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Abstract: This study aims to determine good corporate governance (KA & DKI), Corporate Social Responsibility on firm value (Tobin's Q) and financial performance (ROA) as moderating variables. This research was conducted on companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange that have a sustainability report. The period used in the study is 2020. The method used for data collection is the documentation method, because the data collected is secondary data in the form of company sustainability reports. The method of collecting data is by browsing the website of each company listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The sample in this study was obtained by purposive sampling method. Based on predetermined criteria, obtained 82 companies. The results of the study indicate that Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the audit committee has an effect on firm value. And financial performance as proxied by ROA can moderate the influence of Good Corporate Governance as proxied by an independent board of commissioners on firm value. Meanwhile, Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the independent board of commissioners and Corporate Social Responsibility has no effect on firm value. And financial performance proxied by ROA cannot moderate the effect of Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the audit committee and financial performance as proxied by ROA cannot moderate the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility on firm value.

Keywords: *good corporate governance, corporate social responsibility, financial performance, company value*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the are of globalization, the development of business world is growing rapidly follows by increasingly fierce competition. Business need to think critically, effectively and efficiently to stand out from the competition.

The financial report is an important report for a company because it contains a report on the company's performance in a certain period that is useful for considering executive decision making. Of course, a company wants its business to continue to grow, perform well financially and have great value as a company and continue to grow from time to time. Increasing the value of the company in the long term is one of its goals.

According to Munawaroh (2014) a good company must be able to control the financial potential and non-financial potential in increasing the company's value for the company's existence in the long term. According to Belia, et al (2017:2263) several factors that greatly affect the value of the company are financial performance, corporate governance, and CSR. According to the company, profit is more important in running a business, because this profit can be used as a measure to assess the company's financial performance.

Good corporate governance is also expected to be able to provide a balance between interests that provide overall benefits for the company. The implementation of good corporate governance is so that companies can face increasingly strong global competition. Good corporate governance aims to revive the company's performance which then affects the value of the company.

Internal Company is a scope that is close to the company and is the initial stage of starting social responsibility. CSR can protect the interests of the company easily if the community accepts the company's presence, then the operations of a company can run smoothly without any disturbance. Corporate Social Responsibility of the company can be seen in the annual report by calculating the index of social disclosure activities (Ardimas, et al 2014:60). The activity index expresses social coverage that includes society, consumer and product protection, labor and the environment. The implementation of a company's CSR is one of the things that affects the company's financial performance.

According to Helfert (2000) financial performance is the result of many management decisions made continuously by managers. Financial performance is related to Return on Assets (ROA) which is used to measure the rate of return on assets. A positive ROA indicates that the total assets used can generate profits for the company and vice versa.

This study replicates the research of Arista Hakiki et al (2019) entitled Good Corporate Governance, Corporate Social Responsibility, Firm Value, And Financial Performance As Moderating Variable. Based on the description that has been explained above, this research is entitled Good Corporate Governance, Corporate Social Responsibility on Company Value and Financial Performance as Moderating Variables (Case Study on Companies Listed on the IDX).

The contribution of this research is shown for the company as a consideration for the company to apply research variables to help increase the value of the company and to evaluate and improve management performance in the future for investors and potential investors. This research is expected to be taken into consideration in assessing the company's performance in making decisions when making investments and for academics, this research is expected to add references, information and theory development regarding Good Corporate Governance proxied by the audit committee and independent board of commissioners, Corporate Social Responsibility on Company Value and Financial Performance as Moderating Variable.

II. Literature Review

Agency Theory

Good Corporate Governance can be understood with the agency theory because it is the main thing for the company. The existence of separation between ownership and management in the company is an important aspect of the agency relationship. This relationship can be explained by a contract that is run principally with an agent, where the owner of the company assigns the manager a task to make decisions based on the agreed work contract (Noviawan and Septiani, 2013).

Legimicaty theory

According to Deegan (2004) Legitimacy Theory is a theory that explains the interaction between companies and society. Legitimacy theory asserts that companies must make efforts to ensure that company activities can be accepted or legitimized by outsiders by operating within the framework and norms that exist in the community or environment where the company is located.

Signaling theory

According to Murnita and Putra (2018), explaining signal theory discusses a company that is needed to be able to provide information to external parties so that it can affect the value of the company reflected in changes in the company's stock price because the market will respond to this information as a signal. Firm value is the normative objective of financial management, namely to maximize firm value and ensure that funds are utilized optimally. The value of the company is a reference for investors regarding their interest in investing. The value of a company can be seen from the company's profits from investing. Firm value is a market value that can increase shareholder prosperity to the maximum if the company's share price increases (Nurlela and Islahuddin, 2008).

Good corporate governance

According to the Ministry of SOEs Article 1 paragraph 1, Regulation of the Minister of State-Owned Enterprises Number: PER-01/MBU/2011 concerning the Implementation of Good Corporate Governance in State-Owned Enterprises, it is stated that GCG are the principles that underlie a process and company management mechanism based on laws and regulations and business ethics. The Corporate Governance mechanism is one of the key elements in increasing economic efficiency which includes a series of relationships between company management, the board of commissioners, shareholders and other stakeholders.

Corporate social responsibility

According to ISO 26000 CSR is an organizational responsibility for the impact of decisions and activities on society and the environment, manifested in the form of transparency and ethical behavior, in line with sustainable development and community welfare, taking into account stakeholder expectations, in line with established laws and norms of behavior international, and integrated with the organization as a whole.

Firm value

Firm value is the normative objective of financial management, namely to maximize firm value and ensure that funds are utilized optimally. The value of the company is a reference for investors regarding their interest in investing. The value of a company can be seen from the company's profits from investing. Firm value is a market value that can increase shareholder prosperity to the maximum if the company's share price increases (Nurlela and Islahuddin, 2008).

Financial performance

According to IAI (2007) financial performance is the company's ability to manage and control resources. Financial performance is an indicator that is able to generate profits for a company. The financial performance of a company can be measured by Return On Assets (ROA). With the assessment of the company's financial performance is an effort to find out the achievements to be achieved by a company as a form of business unit that is mostly carried out by parties with an interest in the existence of the company. According to Putri (2009), there are two kinds of performance measured in various studies, namely the company's operating performance and market performance. Return on Assets (ROA) is a form of profitability ratio to measure a company's ability to cover all the funds that have been invested in activities used for the operating activities of a company.

Research Framework

Figure 2.1 Research Framework

III. INDENTATIONS AND EQUATIONS

Research methods

Population, Sample, and Research Data

The population in this study are companies listed on the IDX that publish a Sustainability Report. The technique used for sampling is the purposive sampling method. And this data was obtained from the website www.idx.co.id. The criteria used for sample selection are as follows:

- a) Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2020 which publishes an annual report.
- b) Companies that have a sustainability report.
- c) Sample companies that have the required completeness of data.

Operational Definition and Variable Measurement Firm value

The dependent variable studied in this study is the firm value measured using Tobin's Q which is calculated using the following formula (Suranta and Merdiastusi, 2004) The CSRI (Corporate Social Responsibility Index) measurement instrument is carried out using a dichotomous approach. The formula for calculating CSRI is (Haniffa et al, 2005) in Sayekti and Wondabio (2007):

Company value can be calculated by the formula:

$$Q = \frac{(EMV + D)}{(EBV + D)}$$

Good corporate governance

Good corporate governance is proxied by an independent audit committee and board of commissioners:

- a) Audit Committee Disclosure (X1)

This variable is measured based on the number of audit committees according to research conducted by Febriyanti and Palupi (2021).

$$\text{Komite audit} = \text{total angka jumlah komite audit}$$

- b) Board of commissioners (X2)

This variable is measured by calculating the percentage of independent commissioners on the board of commissioners according to research conducted by Ratih and Setyarini (2014).

$$DKI = \frac{\text{jumlah anggota dewan komisaris independen}}{\text{jumlah total anggota dewan komisaris}}$$

Corporate social responsibility

The CSRI (Corporate Social Responsibility Index) measurement instrument is carried out using a dichotomous approach. The formula for calculating CSRI is (Haniffa et al, 2005) in Sayekti and Wondabio (2007): The company's financial performance can be measured by return on assets (ROA). The ROA calculation formula is research from Aridini and Susanto (2016)

$$CSRI_j = \frac{\sum X_{ij}}{n_j}$$

Financial performance

The company's financial performance can be measured by return on assets (ROA). The ROA calculation formula is research from Aridini and Susanto (2016)

ROA in this study is calculated by the formula:

$$ROA = \frac{\text{laba bersih setelah pajak}}{\text{total aktiva}}$$

Data Analysis Model

The test model used to test the hypothesis in this study is the method of multiple linear regression analysis using a significance value of 5%. The regression model of this research is:

$$Y = a + (B_1.KA) + (B_2.DKI) + (B_3.CSR) + (B_4.KK) + e$$

$$Y = a + (B_1.KA) + (B_2.DKI) + (B_3.CSR) + (B_4.KK) + (B_5.KA*KK) + (B_6.DKI*KK) + (B_7.CSR*KK) + e$$

Information:

- Y = Firm Value
- a = Constant
- KA = Audit Committee
- DKI = Independent Board Of Commissioners
- CSR = Corporate Social Responsibility
- KK = Financial Performance
- $\beta_1-\beta_5$ = Constant Value
- e = Random error
- 1,2,3,4,5 = Regression Coefficient

IV. FIGURES AND TABLES

Results of Analysis and Discussion

Multiple regression analysis requires a classical assumption test before testing the regression equation. The results of the classical assumption test in this study areas follows.

Table 4.1 Normality test

	Unstandardized	Conclusion
	Residual	
asymp.Sig(2-tailed)	0.950	Normal

Source: Secondary Data Processed, 2022

Testing for normality in this study used the Kolmogorov Smirnov test. Based on the results of the normality test, the sig value of $0.950 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that all research variables in the regression model are normally distributed.

Table 4.2 Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
KA	0,787	1,271	Multicollinearity does not occur
DKI	0,880	1,137	Multicollinearity does not occur
CSR	0,690	1,449	Multicollinearity does not occur
ROA	0,780	1,218	Multicollinearity does not occur

Source: Secondary Data Processed, 2022

Multicollinearity testing is done by looking at the Tolerance Value (TV) and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If the TV value > 0.10 and VIF. it can be seen that all independent variables have a VIF value < 10 and a tolerance value $>$

0.01 . Based on the results of the multicollinearity test, it can be concluded that the data passed the multicollinearity test or there was no multicollinearity.

Table 4.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Sig	Information
KA	0,394	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
DKI	0,063	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
CSR	0,115	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
ROA	0,364	Heteroscedasticity does not occur

Source: Secondary Data Processed, 2022

Heteroscedasticity testing aims to test whether the regression model has an inequality of variance from the residuals in one observation to another. Heteroscedasticity test in this study is to use the glejser test. Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, it can be concluded that all independent variables pass the heteroscedasticity test or there is no heteroscedasticity.

Table 4.4 Autocorrelation Test

Du	Durbin Watson	4-Du	Information
1,7446	1,833	2,2554	Autocorrelation does not occur

Source: Secondary Data Processed, 2022

The Durbin-Watson value is between DU DW (4-DU), $1.7446 < 1.833 < 2.2554$. Based on the results of the autocorrelation test, it can be concluded that the data does not occur autocorrelation or passes the autocorrelation test. The results of the normality test were shown using the CLT (Central Limit Theorem) test. Therefore, the number of samples in the study greater than 30 samples is said to be normally distributed. The research data amounted to 82, so the data can be concluded to be normally distributed.

Normality Test

The results of the normality test were shown using the CLT (Central Limit Theorem) test. Therefore, the number of samples in the study greater than 30 samples is said to be normally distributed. The research data amounted to 82, so the data can be concluded to be normally distributed.

Tabel 4.5 Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Sig	Information
DKI	0,067	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
CSR	0,876	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
ROA	0,545	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
KA*ROA	0,600	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
DKI*ROA	0,545	Heteroscedasticity does not occur
CSR*ROA	0,547	Heteroscedasticity does not occur

Source : Secondary Data Processed, 2022

Heteroscedasticity testing aims to test whether the model has an inequality of variance from the residuals in one observation to another. Heteroscedasticity test in this study is to use the Spearman rank test. Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, it can be said that the moderating data passed the heteroscedasticity test or there was no heteroscedasticity.

Tabel 4.6 Autocorrelation Test

Du	Durbin Watson	4-Du	Information
1,7446	2,179	2,2554	Autocorrelation does not occur

Source: Secondary Data Processed, 2022

The Durbin-Watson value is between DU DW (4-DU), $1.7446 < 2.179 < 2.2554$. Based on the results of the autocorrelation test, it can be concluded that the moderating data does not occur autocorrelation or passes the autocorrelation test.

Table 4.7 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

Variable	B	T	Sig
KA	-0,388	-2,186	0,038
DKI	-0,287	-1,707	0,099
CSR	0,380	2,003	0,055
ROA	0,217	1,218	0,234
KA*ROA	0,246	0,106	0,916
DKI*ROA	44,033	6,087	0,000
CSR*ROA	-58,031	-1,360	0,179
Variable	B	F	Sig
Uji F	-	21,023	0,000
Variabel	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²
Model 1	0,843	0,710	0,677

Source : secondary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis, it is known that the multiple linear regression equations are:

$$Y = 1,449 - 0,388 KA - 0,287 DKI + 0,380 CSR + 0,287 ROA + 0,246 KA*ROA + 44,033 DKI*ROA - 58,031 CSR*ROA + e$$

The regression equation has the following meaning:

The constant value (α) is **1,449** which means that if Good corporate governance, corporate social responsibility, financial performance, financial performance moderates good corporate governance, financial performance moderates corporate social responsibility is 0 (zero), then the firm value level remains at 1.449.

The value of the regression coefficient on the audit committee variable is -0,388 with a negative sign (-). This shows that if profitability increases by 1 (unit) then the value of the company will increase by -0,388.

The value of the regression coefficient on the independent board of commissioners variable is -0.287 with a negative sign (-). This shows that if the independent board of commissioners decreases by 1 (unit) then the value of the company will decrease by -0.287.

The value of the regression coefficient on the corporate social responsibility variable is 0.380 with a positive sign (+). This shows that if corporate social responsibility increases by 1 (unit) then the value of the company will increase by 0.380.

The value of the regression coefficient on the financial performance variable is 0.287 with a positive sign (+). This shows that if the financial performance increases by 1 (unit), the firm value will increase by 0.287.

The value of the regression coefficient on the financial performance variable moderating the audit committee is 0.246 with a positive sign (+). This shows that if the audit committee's moderating financial performance increases by 1 (unit), the firm value will increase by 0.246.

The value of the regression coefficient on the financial performance variable that moderates the independent board of commissioners is 44,033 with a positive sign (+). This shows that if the moderating financial performance of the independent board of commissioners increases by 1 (unit), the firm value will increase by 44,033.

The value of the regression coefficient on the financial performance variable moderating corporate social

responsibility is -58,031 with a negative sign (-). This shows that if the moderate financial performance of corporate social responsibility decreases by 1 (unit), the firm value will decrease by -58.031.

TUji test

Based on the results of the f test in the table above, it is obtained that F count of 22, 222 is greater than F table of 2,368 with a significance of 0.000 or less than 2,368. So it can be concluded that simultaneously (simultaneous) the variables of profitability, liquidity, activity, dividend policy, and firm size have an effect on firm value. Thus the regression model used in this study shows *goodness of fit*. Based on the results of the T test, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The influence of the audit committee on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is -0.036 and the t-count value is -2.186 with a significance value of 0.038. The significance value is smaller than the specified fault tolerance ($0.038 < 0.05$). This shows that the audit committee has a negative and significant effect on firm value, so the first hypothesis (a) is accepted.

2. Influence of independent board of commissioners on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is -0.265 and the t-count value is -1.707 with a significance value of 0.099. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.099 > 0.05$). This shows that the independent board of commissioners has no effect on firm value, so the first hypothesis (b) is rejected.

3. Effect of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 1.138 and the t-count value is 2.003 with a significance value of 0.055. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.055 > 0.05$). This shows that CSR has no effect on firm value, so the second hypothesis is rejected.

4. Financial performance moderates the influence of the audit committee on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 0.246 and the t-count value is 0.106 with a significance value of 0.916. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.916 > 0.05$). This shows that financial performance does not moderate the effect of the audit committee on firm value, so the third hypothesis (a) is rejected.

5. Financial performance moderates the influence of independent commissioners on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 44.033 and the t-count value is 6.087 with a significance value of 0.000. The significance value is smaller than the specified error tolerance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This shows that financial performance can moderate the positive and significant effect of independent commissioners on firm value, so that the third hypothesis (b) is accepted.

6. Financial performance moderates the effect of CSR on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is -58.031 and the t-count value is -1.360 with a significance value of 0.179. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.179 > 0.05$). This shows that financial performance does not moderate the negative and insignificant effect of CSR on firm value, so the fourth hypothesis is rejected.

FUjitest

Based on the test results, the f-count value is 21.023 and the f-table value is 2.72 with a significance value of 0.000. The significance value is smaller than the specified error tolerance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This shows that financial performance moderates the effect of the audit committee, independent board of commissioners and CSR together on firm value in a moderating regression equation.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

Based on the test results obtained adjusted R² of 0.677. This shows that the ability of the audit committee, independent commissioners, and CSR which is moderated by financial performance on firm value is 67.7% while the remaining 32.3% is influenced by other variables outside the model.

Discussion of Analysis Results

1. The influence of the on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is -0.036 and the t-count value is -2.186 with a significance value of 0.038. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.038 > 0.05$). This shows that the audit committee has a negative and significant effect on firm value, so the first hypothesis (a) is accepted. The greater the number of members of the audit committee, the greater the responsibility to oversee the process of reporting and disclosure of financial statements. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Kartika, etc. (2021), Yusuf and Wiguna (2019), and Dahlia (2018).

2. Influence of independent board of commissioners on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is -0.265 and the t-count value is -1.707 with a significance value of 0.099. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.099 > 0.05$). This shows that the independent board of commissioners has no effect on firm value, so the first hypothesis (b) is rejected. The smaller the number of independent commissioners, the smaller the supervisory function in monitoring management actions within the company. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Susyanti, et al (2020), Sondokan, etc. (2019), and Dahlia (2018).

3. Effect of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 1.138 and the t-count value is 2.003 with a significance value of 0.055. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.055 > 0.05$). This shows that CSR has no effect on firm value, so the second hypothesis is rejected. Disclosure of CSR in the company has not been able to increase the value of the company and companies that do not disclose a CSR do not necessarily have a low company value. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Sari (2018), Panggabean (2018), and Priantinah and Retno (2012). Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 0.246 and the t-count value is 0.106 with a significance value of 0.916. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.916 > 0.05$). This shows that financial performance does not moderate the audit committee on firm value, so the third hypothesis (a) is rejected. Many members of the audit committee can result in inefficient for a company because there are many tasks that will be divided, this can cause members of the audit committee to be less focused in carrying out their duties so that the company's performance will get worse. So this research can be concluded that financial performance does not strengthen the relationship of the audit committee to firm value. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Fidiana and Purwitaningsari (2021), Asyik and Nugraha (2021).

4. Financial performance moderates the influence of the audit committee on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 0.246 and the t-count value is 0.106 with a significance value of 0.916. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.916 > 0.05$). This shows that financial performance does not moderate the audit committee on firm value, so the third hypothesis (a) is rejected. Many members of the audit committee can result in inefficient for a company because there are many tasks that will be divided, this can cause members of the audit committee to be less focused in carrying out their duties so that the company's performance will get worse. So this research can be concluded that financial performance does not strengthen the relationship of the audit committee to firm value. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Fidiana and Purwitaningsari (2021), Asyik and Nugraha (2021).

5. Financial performance moderates the influence of independent commissioners on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is 44.033 and the t-count value is 6.087 with a significance value of 0.000. The significance value is smaller than the specified error tolerance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This shows that financial performance can moderate the positive and significant effect of independent commissioners on firm value, so that the third hypothesis (b) is accepted. So it can be concluded that the higher the financial performance of the company, the higher the value of the company. And the number of independent commissioners must also be considered because if the number of independent commissioners is too small, the supervisory function will not work properly in monitoring management actions within the company. So this research can be concluded that financial performance can strengthen the relationship of independent board of commissioners to firm value. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Prasetya (2021).

6. Financial performance moderates the effect of CSR on firm value

Based on the test results, the regression coefficient value is -58.031 and the t-count value is -1.360 with a significance value of 0.179. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.179 > 0.05$). This shows that financial performance does not moderate CSR on firm value, so the fourth hypothesis is rejected. The higher the financial performance of the company, the higher the value of the company will be. A company will provide information to increase the value of the company. Investors appreciate the information disclosed by CSR for decision making. So this research can be concluded that financial performance does not strengthen the relationship of CSR to firm value. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Badarudin and Wuryani (2018).

CONCLUSION

1. The effect of Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the audit committee has a negative and significant effect on firm value. This is evidenced by the regression coefficient value of -0.067 and the t-count value of -0.875 with a significance value of 0.038. The significance value is smaller than the specified fault tolerance ($0.038 < 0.05$).
2. The effect of Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the independent board of commissioners has a negative and insignificant effect on firm value. This is evidenced by the regression coefficient value of -0.265 and the t-count value of -1.707 with a significance value of 0.099. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.099 > 0.05$).
3. The influence of Corporate Social Responsibility has no effect on firm value. This is evidenced by the regression coefficient value of 1.138 and the t-count value of 2.003 with a significance value of 0.055. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.055 > 0.05$).
4. Financial performance as proxied by ROA cannot moderate the effect of Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the audit committee on firm value. This is evidenced by the regression coefficient value of 0.246 and the t-count value of 0.106 with a significance value of 0.916. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.916 > 0.05$).
5. Financial performance as proxied by ROA can moderate the effect of Good Corporate Governance as proxied by an independent board of commissioners on firm value. This is evidenced by the regression coefficient value of 44.033 and the t-count value of 6.087 with a significance value of 0.000. The significance value is greater than the specified fault tolerance ($0.000 < 0.05$).
6. Financial performance as proxied by ROA cannot moderate the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility on firm value. This is evidenced by the regression coefficient value of -58.031 and the t-count value of -1.360 with a significance value of 0.179. The significance value is smaller than the specified fault tolerance ($0.179 > 0.05$).

Limitations and Suggestions

1. This study only examines several factors that affect firm value, while there are many other factors that affect firm value such as size, profitability, etc.
2. The sample companies in this study are limited because only a few companies issue sustainability reports.
3. Future research is expected to improve the limitations contained in this study.
4. Further research is expected to add years of research in order to obtain accurate research results in the long term.

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